

An Identity Key Management System with Deterministic Key Hierarchy for SSI-native Internet of Things

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ABSTRACT

The key to secure implementation of the Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) model in IoT nodes is the Key Management System (KMS). A KMS for a large number of identity key pairs, bound to an appropriate combination of the IoT node hardware and firmware, and possibly running in a Trusted Execution Environment to ensure a high level of trust in the cryptographic operations. This paper presents the design of a novel KMS for IoT nodes, which adapts the principles of the deterministic key hierarchy used by cryptocurrency wallets to provide trusted key pair generation and usage to SSI frameworks. The implementation of the solution on a constrained IoT node demonstrates its feasibility.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Security and privacy** → **Key management**; *Human and societal aspects of security and privacy.*

KEYWORDS

Self-Sovereign Identity, Key Management System, Hierarchical Deterministic Wallet, DLT, IoT

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1 INTRODUCTION

The Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) [13, 15] is an emerging decentralized digital identity model that gives an IoT node full control over the data it uses to build and prove its identity. This model provides a viable alternative to the centralised Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) model, reducing the complexity and associated costs of X.509 certificate management in large-scale IoT systems [11].

The SSI reference model consists of three layers depicted in Figure 1. Each layer contributes to the generation of the identity and defines the basic principles for trustable interactions with the other nodes.

Figure 1: Self-Sovereign Identity stack.

Layer 1 is implemented by any Verifiable Data Registry (VDR). When the VDR is implemented by a Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) it acts as the root of trust for public identity data. In fact, they are distributed and immutable means of storage by design [5].

The Decentralized Identifier (DID) [18] is a new type of globally unique identifier designed to verify a node. The DID is a Uniform Resource Identifier (URI) in the form

`did:method_name:method_specific_id`

where `method-name` is the name of the DID method used to interact with the VDR and `method-specific-id` is the pointer to the DID document stored in the registry. Optionally, the URI includes the component network to specify the particular network of choice (e.g. `mainnet`, `testnet`, etc.) between the `method_name` and `method_specific_id`. Thus, DIDs associate a node with a DID document [18] to enable trusted interactions with it. Appendix A presents an example of a DID document containing the DID and two verification methods with an Ed25519 and a Secp256k1 public key for authentication purposes. The two public keys are referenced by different `#fragment` values which are the components that follow the first number sign character of the DID in each `id` property.

The DID method [18] is a software implementation used by a node to interact with the VDR of choice. Following W3C recommendation [18], a DID method provides the so-called CRUD functionalities to

- **Create** a DID: generates an identity key pair (sk_{id}, pk_{id}) for authentication purposes, the corresponding DID document containing the public key pk_{id} and stores the DID document in the registry at the `method-specific-id` pointed to by the DID,
- **Resolve** a DID: retrieves the DID document from the `method-specific-id` on the registry pointed to by the DID,

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- **Update** a DID: update the content of the DID document, *e.g.* generates a new key pair (sk'_{id}, pk'_{id}) , and store the modified DID document to the same or a new method-specific-id if the node needs to change the DID, and
- **Deactivate** a DID: provides evidence in the registry that the DID has been revoked by the owner.

The DID method implementation is registry-specific and makes the upper layers independent of the VDR of choice.

Layer 2 uses DIDs and DID documents to establish a cryptographic trust between two nodes. In principle, both nodes prove the ownership of their private key sk_{id} bound to the public key pk_{id} in their DID document stored in the registry.

While Layer 2 uses DID technology (*i.e.* the security foundation of the SSI model) to start authentication, Layer 3 completes it and also deals with authorisation to services and/or resources using Verifiable Credentials (VCs) [20]. A VC is a digital credential that contains additional characteristics of a node's identity beyond its identity key pair and the DID.

The combination of identity key pairs, DIDs, and VCs shapes the digital identity of a person or an object in the SSI model.

The key to secure implementations of the SSI model in IoT nodes is the Key Management System (KMS). In the authors' opinion, a management system for a large number of identity key pairs (sk_{id}, pk_{id}) , bound to a proper combination of the IoT node's hardware and firmware, and possibly running in a Trusted Execution Environment (TEE) to ensure a high level of trust in the isolation, access control and validity of key material and cryptographic operations (*e.g.* *Open-TEE* [8], *Keystone* [6]).

This paper presents the design of a KMS for SSI native IoT nodes, which adapts the principles of the deterministic key hierarchy used by cryptocurrency wallets to provide trusted key pair generation, signature and signature verification to any SSI framework dealing with the DIDs and VCs components. Typically, SSI frameworks provide interfaces to plug different KMS implementations [3, 4, 22].

Regardless of the specific implementation, our design assumes that a *seed* bound to the hardware and firmware of the IoT node becomes available after boot and loaded in the volatile memory region protected for the TEE and used to derive the *master secret* of the entire deterministic key hierarchy. This design choice allows the KMS to generate any key pair and use the private key for any cryptographic purpose without having to deal with the complexities of storing and destroying key material. This is a significant advantage over traditional KMSs that have to deal with the secure storage and destruction of key materials. In this paper, a novel design is proposed that will allow (i) the generation of a large number of key pairs to be used in different verification methods of DID documents, and to support the use of different DIDs that are unique to each interaction to reduce correlation risks, and (ii) the generation of key pairs on different elliptic curves to support different cryptographic choices. At the core of our design, there is a deterministic key hierarchy to handle identity keys. We designed a new hierarchy as an extension of the one presented in the design document BIP-32 [21]. BIP-32 defines how to build hierarchical deterministic cryptocurrency wallets by defining the algorithms to derive a tree of key pairs starting from a single seed. We have

extended the tree by defining a new hierarchy and by modifying the derivation algorithm to also support the SSI purpose.

2 RELATED WORK

There are several papers in the academic literature on the design and use of diverse types of identity wallets in a variety of use cases.

The work in [2] assumes the use of a mobile identity wallet for sharing in an anonymous fashion cyber threat information on a common open platform. The security of the wallet is given for granted; the authors suggest storing the private key in the secure key store on the mobile application, but they do not provide any more information on the update and or recovery process.

The authors in [17] address the design of a privacy-enhanced cloud-based wallet for a custodial approach. A user can store his data in the wallet in the cloud in an encrypted form and authorize the cloud-based wallet to share identity data with data recipients. The focus of the paper is on the privacy by design methodology and it does not address key management issues.

In [16] the authors examine an SSI digital wallet and provide a practical decentralized key recovery solution using Shamir's secret sharing scheme and Hyperledger Indy DLT. The paper focuses on a practical key backup and recovery protocol based on threshold secret sharing cryptography. The protocol relies on multiple third-party key escrow providers in which each participant holds a share of the user's secret key. The secret key can only be correctly recovered when a sufficient number of participants are involved.

An in-depth analysis of the features that an SSI digital wallet must support to provide a high level of assurance is presented in [1]. In this solution, the two key pairs used in the registration and authentication phases are randomly generated, and one of them is generated by tamper-proof hardware (*e.g.* HW token). The lack of key backup/recovery is discussed by the authors themselves as a drawback.

The paper [12] reviews with a systemic methodology the academic literature on identity digital wallets. It analyzes and compares existing definitions, features and capabilities of several solutions. One main aspect that emerges from the analysis of the solutions is that secure storage of key pairs, locally and/or remotely, and key backup/recovery are largely covered. In principle, this means that they use random identity key generation and that each key is independent of the others.

To the best of our knowledge, our work is the first that proposes to use a deterministic hierarchy for identity key management. The proposed solution removes the need to implement secure storage and/or Shamir's secret sharing strategy, hence enhancing the performance and security of the key management strategy. In addition, our work enables comprehensive management of identity and cryptocurrency keys within the same KMS.

3 HIERARCHY FOR DETERMINISTIC CRYPTOCURRENCY WALLETS

The BIP-32 [21] design document describes hierarchical deterministic wallets as the combination of a hierarchy and two algorithms for deriving a tree of key pairs to make cryptocurrency transactions. A first algorithm for deriving private keys and a second one to derive the public keys. BIP-43 [7] and BIP-44 [9] further describe the

logical hierarchy and solve some interoperability issues. In practice, these documents define a 5-level path to derive a tree of key pairs from a single master key m derived from a *seed*. The master secret key corresponds to the first 256 bits of the output of an HMAC-SHA512 of the *seed*; the key of the HMAC function is the string "Bitcoin seed". The path looks like this:

$$m/purpose'/coin_type'/$$

$$account'/change/address_index$$

Each level of the path is 32-bit long and has a special meaning:

- **purpose** is an integer set to 44' in accordance to BIP-43 and indicates derivation of keys for cryptocurrencies.
- **coin_type** is an integer whose value is associated with a specific cryptocurrency in the SLIP-44 [14] design document; this level is intended to create a separate sub-tree for each cryptocurrency, so to avoid reusing addresses across different networks for privacy reasons.
- **account** is an integer whose value is used to partition the key space into independent user identities so that the wallet never mixes cryptocurrencies across accounts; accounts are numbered sequentially from index 0, and the index value is used as the child index in BIP-32 derivation.
- **change** is an integer set to either 0 or 1 to derive keys associated with addresses used to receive or send funds respectively.
- **address_index** is an integer from index 0 in a sequentially increasing manner that identifies a public address on the blockchain.

The integer values in a path realization are used to generate a secret key at each level of the tree. A secret key derivation algorithm generates a private child key from the private parent key as detailed in the Algorithm 1. The BIP-32 design document defines k_{par} and K_{par} as the parent private and public key respectively, $x_{K_{par}}$ as the x coordinate of the public parent key, c_{par} as the chain code of the parent secret key (i.e. an extra 256 bits of entropy used at each derivation), i the value of the path at i^{th} level, and n is the elliptic curve order set to the Secp256k1's order by default.

The couple ($new_key, chain_code$) is called extended key and its components are used as the inputs (i.e. k_{par}, c_{par}) of the next iteration. Once derived the last secret key k_i , the corresponding public key K_i is simply computed as $K_i = k_i * G$ where G is the curve's generator. For the sake of completeness, BIP-32 also provides an algorithm for deriving a tree of public keys from the public master key $M = m * G$.

It is worth noting that Algorithm 1 is forced to use hardened derivation (Line 2) in the first three levels of the path, while it uses public derivation (Line 5) in the last two levels. The apostrophe in the path indicates that BIP-32 hardened derivation is used. The reason behind this design choice is to protect the entire generation process from the *reverse key derivation attack* that can reveal the master key m .

Algorithm 1: private parent key \rightarrow private child key derivation.

Inputs: k_{par}, c_{par}, i . Constant: $n = 2^{256}$

```

1 if  $i \geq 2^{31}$  then
2    $I = \text{HMAC} - \text{SHA512}_{c_{par}}(0x00 || k_{par} || i)$ 
3 else
4    $K_{par} = k_{par} * G$ 
5    $I = \text{HMAC} - \text{SHA512}_{c_{par}}(0x02 \text{ or } 0x03 || x_{K_{par}} || i)$ 
6  $I_L = I[: 32]$ 
7  $I_R = I[32 :]$ 
8  $k_i = I_L + k_{par} \pmod{n}$ 
9  $chain\_code = I_R$ 
10  $new\_key = k_i$ 
11 if  $I_L = 0$  or  $I_L \geq n$  then
12    $\text{discard } new\_key$ 
13 else
14   return ( $new\_key, chain\_code$ )

```

4 IDENTITY KEY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

4.1 Identity Path

The path for deriving identity key pairs for the SSI model may follow the same principles presented in Section 3 but with a structure consistent with the model and representations of DID and DID document specified in [18] by W3C. The proposed identity path comprises 6 levels after the master key m derived from a single *seed*. The master secret key corresponds to the first 256 bits of the output of an HMAC-SHA512 of the *seed*; the key of the HMAC function is the string "Bitcoin seed". The identity path looks like this:

$$m/purpose'/method_name'/network'/$$

$$method_specific_id'/verification_method'/$$

$$fragment'$$

Figure 2 shows the proposed identity path, each level of the path is 32-bit long and has a special meaning:

- **purpose** is an integer set to 1361' following the BIP-43 design document; it indicates that the sub-tree is for identity keys¹.
- **method_name** is an integer associated with the implementation of the DID method used by the IoT node to interact with the VDR of choice.
- **network** is an integer associated with the specific network deployment selected as the VDR.
- **method_specific_id** is an integer conversion of the `method_specific_id` component of the DID, reduced modulus 2^{32} to respect the constraint whereby each parent key can at most have 2^{32} child keys.
- **verification_method** is an integer value associated with the type of verification method in the DID document (e.g. the DID document in Section 1 expresses two methods of type

¹The digits of the number 1361 in *base16* are 551, which are similar to the word SSI.

Figure 2: The identity path.

Table 1: List of integer values associated with verification methods used in DID documents

Integer	Verification Method Type
0	general verification
1	authentication
2	assertion
3	key agreement
4	capability invocation
5	capability delegation

authentication); Table 1 shows the binding between integer value and type.

- **fragment** is an integer conversion of the `method_specific_id` component of the DID, reduced modulus 2^{32} to respect the constraint whereby each parent key can at most have 2^{32} child keys.

Note that W3C is maintaining a table with the available DID method specifications [19], the table can be the starting point for a new registry to bind `method_name` and `network` to a proper integer value.

4.2 Identity Key Derivation Algorithm

Each realization of the identity path is used to derive the key pairs with a customized key derivation algorithm. The main difference from cryptocurrency key derivation is that the identity keys can belong to different elliptic curves. The DID document in Section 1 shows a practical case where an IoT node has two identity key pairs on the Ed25519 and Secp256k1 curves.

Algorithm 2: private parent key \rightarrow private child key derivation.

Inputs: k_{par}, c_{par}, i . Variable: n

```

1  $I = \text{HMAC} - \text{SHA512}_{c_{par}}(0x00 || k_{par} || i)$ 
2  $I_L = I[: 32]$ 
3  $I_R = I[32 :]$ 
4  $k_i = I_L + k_{par} \pmod n$ 
5  $chain\_code = I_R$ 
6  $new\_key = k_i$ 
7 if  $I_L = 0$  or  $I_L \geq n$  then
8   | discard  $new\_key$ 
9 else
10  | return ( $new\_key, chain\_code$ )

```

CHANGE 1. Let I_L be the first 32 bytes of HMAC output in Algorithm 1 (Lines 2 and 6) and let k_{par} be the parent private key. If the child key curve is different from the parent key curve, then $k_i = I_L + k_{par} \pmod n$ where n modulo the order of the child key curve. In BIP-32, n is a constant because the curve never changes.

Note that the discussion on the identity key derivation algorithm assumes the use of elliptic curves with 32- or 33-bytes long keys. The modifications required to support curves with longer keys (e.g. Secp384r1) are straightforward.

The key derivation principles in BIP-32 permit public key derivation in the last two levels of the path to support some specific cryptocurrency-related use cases. In the case of identity there is no need to use public key derivation and the protection to the *reverse key derivation attack* must be adopted at each derivation.

CHANGE 2. The hardened derivation is used at all levels of the identity path, so checking the value of i is no longer necessary.

Therefore, given the design choices made, the identity key derivation is described by Algorithm 2. The order of the elliptic curve n is set to Secp256k1's order in the first five levels and to the order of the requested elliptic curve at the last level. Once derived the last secret key k_i , the corresponding public key K_i is simply computed as $K_i = k_i * G$ where G is the curve's generator.

4.3 Design discussion

The combination of the proposed identity key derivation and of a TEE makes the resulting KMS trustworthy for any SSI framework implementing the CRUD functionalities discussed in Section 1. The design of the identity path and the working principles of the identity key derivation algorithm make the KMS more secure than other solutions that have to deal with secure storage, Shamir's secret sharing of centrally generated private keys, or distributed generation of private keys. The identity private keys are derived on demand, used in cryptographic operations (e.g. signature), and then may be removed from the TEE protected memory.

The intrinsic advantage of the proposed approach is even more relevant since the proposed SSI-native IoT node can handle multiple key pairs from a single *seed* protected by the TEE. The proposed identity key hierarchy supports the use of multiple DID methods

(i.e. different VDRs) and for each verification method type expressed in a DID document multiple key pairs on different elliptic curves.

In addition, the deterministic key hierarchy facilitates the recovery operation of all the identity private keys after a reboot or a device failure. In both cases, an IoT node randomly generating the key pairs and without a permanent secure storage solution would be forced to re-anchor the DID documents in the VDRs, with the associated delay and cost (i.e. writing to immutable VDRs is typically slow and costly).

An IoT node adopting the proposed solution can maintain the previously anchored DID documents to the DVRs and be ready to operate without any further delay and facing new costs, because the deterministic key hierarchy is ready to derive the private keys right after the boot. Of course, an operator can create a new, fresh key tree when needed, with a simple software update that results in the generation of a different master key.

Finally, the proposed identity path assumes the use of the Secp256k1 curve from the first to the fifth level and then supports the change of the elliptic curve at the fragment level to meet the requirement of supporting different verification methods (i.e. public key types) as defined by the DID core recommendation [18]. Choosing the Secp256k1 curve at the root of the tree as in BIP-32 allows a unique key hierarchy from the same master key to generate identity and cryptocurrency keys. This option is intended to enable new IoT applications using VDRs for trust-in-data purposes or decentralized Byzantine fault-tolerant distributed computation through smart contracts.

The SLIP-44 [14] design document provides the information to derive the public and private keys for different cryptocurrency types.

5 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

We implemented the Algorithm 2 to assess the performance on a constrained IoT device.

We selected the B-U585I-IOT02A Discovery kit. It provides a complete demonstration and development platform for the STM32U585AI microcontroller, featuring an ARM Cortex-M33 core running up to 160 MHz with ARM TrustZone, 2 Mbytes of Flash memory and 786 Kbytes of SRAM. The platform runs the algorithm's implementations in bare metal.

We assessed the performance in terms of timing for identity key generation and stack size required for the implementation. Looking at the overall identity key derivation Algorithm 2, the most demanding operations are the derivation of the master key m and then HMAC function and module n calculation (Line 1 and 4) of the Algorithm 2 respectively. The master key generation from the *seed* lasts 16 ms. The identity key generation requires 150 ms to go through the six levels. Therefore the overall derivation latency is about 166 ms.

Concerning the usage of the stack memory, the overall code requires approximately 1790 bytes. This is about 0.2% of the overall SRAM size.

6 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper has presented the design of a novel KMS for SSI native IoT nodes, which adapts the principles of the deterministic key hierarchy used by cryptocurrency wallets to provide trusted key pair

generation and usage to any SSI framework. The implementation of a novel identity path and Identity key derivation algorithm on a constrained IoT node demonstrates the feasibility of the design.

Note that, the identity path and key derivation algorithm can also potentially be used in digital wallets for people. In this case, the *seed* would be generated from a wordlist (i.e. 12 words) optionally protected by an additional passphrase as specified in [10]. In this further scenario, the proposed solution with its ability to deterministically derive existing keys provides the benefit of (i) regaining access to existing identities, simplifying the recovery process, and (ii) facilitating the seamless transition of existing identities to a new device.

Future work will focus on two directions. First, the design of an identity key derivation algorithm using Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC) to support Post-Quantum (PQ) and Traditional (T) key generation and PQ/T hybrid signatures. Second, the decomposition of the functionalities of a general-purpose SSI framework (i.e. a library implementing DID- and VC-related functionalities) between the trusted and untrusted zone of an IoT node featuring a TEE.

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A DID DOCUMENT

This is an example of W3C compliant DID document.

```
"id": "did:method_name:method_specific_id",
"authentication": [{
```

```
  "id": "did:method_name:method_spec_id#keys-1",
  "type": "JsonWebKey2020",
  "controller": "did:method_name:method_spec_id",
  "publicKeyJwk": {
    "crv": "Ed25519",
    "x": ".. x coordinate ..",
    "kty": "OKP",
    "kid": ".. key thumbprint .."
  }
}, {
  "id": "did:method_name:method_spec_id#keys-2",
  "type": "JsonWebKey2020",
  "controller": "did:method_name:method_spec_id",
  "publicKeyJwk": {
    "crv": "Secp256k1",
    "x": ".. x coordinate ..",
    "y": ".. y coordinate ..",
    "kty": "EC",
    "kid": ".. key thumbprint .."
  }
}]
```